

SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF HARMONIZING THE AESTHETIC TASTE AND ARTISTIC THINKING OF YOUNG PEOPLE BASED ON UZBEK NATIONAL MUSIC

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ABSTRACT

The article studies the theoretical and methodological issues of developing the artistic and aesthetic thinking of young people based on Uzbek national music, the socio-philosophical aspects of developing the artistic and aesthetic thinking of young people based on Uzbek national music, and the priority tasks of developing the artistic and aesthetic thinking of young people based on Uzbek national music. The theoretical foundations of developing the artistic and aesthetic thinking of young people based on Uzbek national music are also analyzed.

Introduction. The aesthetic taste of young people is considered one of the key indicators of an individual's spiritual maturity. It reflects a person's ability to perceive beauty, evaluate artistic values, and express an aesthetic attitude toward reality. From a philosophical perspective, aesthetic taste manifests as an emotional-imaginative form of human cognition, shaped under the influence of consciousness, culture, and the social environment. Therefore, the development of aesthetic taste among youth is not only an issue of education but also an актуал topic within broader socio-philosophical research.

Literature Review And Methods. The theoretical and methodological issues of developing the artistic and aesthetic thinking of youth based on Uzbek national music, as well as its socio-philosophical aspects and priority tasks, have been analyzed in the scientific works of scholars such as G. Matyoqubova, F. Asqar, I.A. G'anieva, G.A. Tursunova, Z. Oripov, Sh.I. Ayxodjaeva, T.V. Cherednichenko, S.F. Gurbanalieva, A.G. Kostyuk, L.S. Cherkashina, N. Yanov-Yanovskaya, A. Boboxonov, S. Jumaev, D. Karomatli, T. Levin, and Yu. Elsner.

Results and discussion. From a socio-philosophical perspective, national music contributes to strengthening national cultural identity among youth and fostering cultural autonomy. Through national musical works, young people engage with their history, traditions, and aesthetic values, linking them to social communication and situating cultural heritage within its historical and spiritual context. Such a rich aesthetic environment helps shape young people not merely as passive recipients of musical works, but as active subjects capable of understanding artistic creativity, analyzing it, and reinterpreting social relations through aesthetic criteria.

The purposeful use of national musical heritage in the educational process enhances young people's aesthetic experience, creative thinking, and cultural communication skills. In this regard, teachers and cultural institutions should facilitate the harmonization of aesthetic

taste and artistic thinking by analyzing examples of national music, creatively reinterpreting them, and encouraging social discussion.

Music as an art form exerts a direct and powerful influence on individuals from an early age and plays a significant role in their overall cultural development. As music occupies an increasingly important place in the cultural life of society, it becomes a constant companion throughout a person's life. Music is the only art that penetrates deeply into the human heart and possesses the power to vividly express emotional experiences.

Musical-aesthetic education should become an integral part of the broader efforts aimed at the harmonious development of individuals in society. Without widespread musical outreach among the population, it is impossible to achieve full and meaningful results. Working with youth in the field of music is of particular importance.

Music evokes strong emotional responses in the human soul. Through music, artistic perception develops and emotional sensitivity becomes richer. Without fostering musical perception in young people and cultivating their interest and love for music, it is impossible to develop their physical, spiritual, and moral qualities in a comprehensive manner. An early interest in music has a profound impact on an individual's subsequent musical development, shaping other skills and tastes, and cultivating refined musical appreciation. Music is a powerful source of aesthetic and spiritual inspiration. It influences individuals throughout their lives, awakening emotions, exciting them, and motivating action. Music inspires, stirs the soul, invigorates, and provides energy. At the same time, a melancholic melody may evoke sorrow and emotional distress. This largely depends on the individual's level of musical perception, listening ability, capacity for comprehension, aesthetic taste, and overall cultural development. Therefore, it is important to define the objectives and content of musical perception, which are determined by the general goals related to the comprehensive development of the individual, including aesthetic education.

Considering the significant influence of music on human emotions and aspirations, as well as on understanding and perceiving its content, the appropriate use of musical works that truthfully and accurately reflect reality is of particular importance. It is well known that the primary source of the formation of musical images is directly connected with harmony with nature and human speech, as well as with the perception of beauty in the surrounding world. Since ancient times, humans have sought to reflect in songs or instrumental performances the sounds of birds they have heard, echoes, the flow of water, and the melodies of insects. For musical art, human thought and emotional expression have served as a fundamental basis. Music influences people's emotions and thinking, enabling an emotional perception of surrounding reality and contributing to its reinterpretation and transformation. Music that embodies a progressive emotional expression affects a person's feelings, thinking, and worldview, guiding them toward certain goals, shaping their attitude toward the environment, and fostering a sense of empathy and goodwill.

In music, the artistic image—the means of creating a musical image—is determined by features unique only to music. This specificity is expressed through the multifaceted elements integrated within melodies, including the intonational development of musical thought, various movements, and emotional states. Melody serves as the leading means of expressing the image; it is enriched by all musical elements (melodic movement, timbre, and others),

harmonized with chords and specific sounds, and connected with all aspects of a musical work. By hearing the initial words accompanied by vivid melodies in an operatic aria or scene, a listener can quickly recognize the characters of classical opera.

In order for music to contribute comprehensively to the upbringing of young people, to facilitate their figurative and emotional perception of the surrounding world, and to influence the formation of adolescent character, the following tasks are defined based on the objectives of music education:

1. To develop the musical abilities of young people.
2. To teach youth singing and musical-rhythmic skills, and to cultivate their ability to perceive, feel, and understand music.
3. To develop artistic and creative abilities in young people.

All these tasks are closely interconnected. Let us consider the first task. What is meant by musicality? This quality encompasses two important aspects:

a) Emotional responsiveness—the ability to empathize with the figurative content of a musical work;

b) The development of musical perception and abilities in young people, enabling them to distinguish the musical-sound material of a composition.

Both aspects of musicality exist in inseparable unity and are developed simultaneously. As musicality develops, young people begin to vividly perceive musical images and the associated surrounding imagery. This, in turn, plays a significant role in understanding the environment, cultivating aesthetic evaluation, forming artistic taste, and fostering a love for music. The musicality of adolescents is developed through their active engagement in musical activities.

Conclusion. A person who enters the mysterious world of music inevitably realizes that it is a boundless ocean. This ocean is characterized by echoes from the past, its formation over time within the laws of space and time, and its continuous, living development based on the divine gift of creativity. It is for this reason that each historical period is defined by its own musical traditions. The notion of music as something celestial or divine is reflected in ancient sources. Humanity, in accordance with its level of spirituality, has shaped its spiritual wealth and developed it across the ages. In this process, every sphere has been refined through the passage of time, enriched by new positive relations, and has demonstrated its fruitful outcomes.

The processes within the field of music—from its ancient values to modern criteria—can only be understood through unique works embodied in melodies. The scope of this is extremely vast and even difficult to fully comprehend. Each nation possesses its own spirituality, enlightenment, and aesthetic values, which have been nurtured throughout life by both national and professional factors. At the core of this lie two major directions of thought: folk (popular) music and the products of individual creative expression.

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